

ELIXIR Commissioned Service

Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP), WP3

D3.5 Blogpost summarising the hackathon outcomes

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This deliverable highlights the FairyMAGs hackathon, held in Freiburg, Australia, and online from October 6–9, 2025. A blog post summarizing the major outcomes of the hackathon is available at: <https://galaxyproject.org/news/2025-10-21-fairymags-hackathon-outcome>. A detailed description of the hackathon's organization, participation, and results is provided in M3.5.

Document info

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Dissemination level	PU

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Galaxy Hub Blog Post about the Hackathon

The blog post about the hackathon is available via: <https://galaxyproject.org/news/2025-10-21-fairymags-hackathon-outcome>, summarizing all major outcomes of the hackathon. A detailed description of the hackathon organization, participation, and outcomes is outlined in M3.5.

Outcomes and expected impact

This deliverable is fully aligned with the Capacity Building activities envisioned in the project plan. The hackathon brought together a diverse group of researchers interested in the field of MAGs building.

Dissemination Plans

The outcome of the hackathon is disseminated via the blog post. The dissemination of individual work tasks is described in M3.5.